

Influence of Corruption on Human Trafficking in Contemporary International System: Impact on Third World Countries

Anietie E. Ekang, PhD

Department of Political Science
Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit
08068714001, ayubongekang@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper examines the influence of corruption on human trafficking in the contemporary international system, with a focus on third-world countries. The study adopted the institutional theory developed by John Meyer and Brian Rowan, which posits that different institutions and agencies of government have essential functions they are to perform for the survival of the society. The study argued that corruption is the major cause of human trafficking in the international system. The central idea of this work is that human trafficking occurred with the active collusion of corrupt officials with the criminal gangs. The study concludes that corruption is the major predictor of human trafficking in third-world countries. It was recommended, among others, that security officials/operatives found guilty of corruption or collusion with criminal elements should be punished and that the government should strengthen security institutions such as EFCC, ICPC, CCB and give them more “teeth” to “bite” criminals and not only to bark.

Introduction

Corruption is a word that evokes both hatred and admiration in almost equal measure. While some detest it and others tacitly embrace it, it is invariably treated with caution in official dealings because of its power to make or mar a public officer. The truth, however, is that many who loudly condemn corruption are often insincere in their denunciation, as they benefit directly or indirectly from its proceeds.

Since Nigeria attained independence in 1960, one incubus that has persistently weighed the nation down is the phenomenon of corruption. This social malaise has so deeply permeated every stratum of our social, political, and economic life that successive governments since 1966 have attempted, albeit unsuccessfully, to extirpate it or at least curb its excesses in public life. This scenario, I believe, has played out across most Third World countries, particularly in Africa, where the fight against corruption has consistently occupied a central place in political and economic discourse.

Corruption, in all its ramifications (whether in the private or public sphere) is a symptom of moral indiscipline and societal decadence. It thrives where integrity is perverted and moral values are in decline. Official corruption has nearly become normalized in the public life of officials in many Third World countries. Brazen embezzlement of public funds, the payment of gratification for duties that are legitimately owed, inflation of contract sums, illegal deductions of percentages from awarded contracts, bribery in employment and job placement, and the diversion of public resources for private use have come to resemble unwritten commandments in the body politic of these societies.

The Concept of Corruption

The most commonly used definitions of corruption for development practitioners are probably those put forward by the World Bank and Transparency International. The world bank's working definition of corruption centres on “the abuse of public power for private benefit”.

Transparency International sees corruption as “the misuse of entrusted power for private gain”.

Wilkins (1970) defines corruption as “a behaviour which is different from or conflicts with the standards which are accepted as normal within a group or social system”. Corruption defined as a departure from accepted standards, presupposes that there are known and agreed standards and what they should be. These standards evolve from commonly shared beliefs, practices and values of a community or social institution. Individual conduct is therefore measured according to the conformity or deviation from the standards (Ikejiani – Clark, 2001). There are always social and institutional means of effecting conformity or dealing with the deviation.

Some scholars have maintained that the concept of public interest is very significant in explaining the phenomenon of corruption. Friedrich (1996) says that;

The pattern of corruption can be said to exist whenever a power holder who is charged with doing certain things, that is, who is responsible functionary or office holder, is by monetary or other rewards not legally provided for, induced to take actions which favour whoever provides the rewards and thereby does damage to the public and its interest.

The emphasis here is placed on public duty which of course is relative and depends on the society one finds himself. What is seen as corruption in one society may not be seen in the same way in another society.

However, there is no single, universally acceptable definition of corruption. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC, 2011), the baseline definition of corruption is the “dishonest or fraudulent conduct by those in power” or “dishonest or illegal behaviour, especially by powerful people”. Corruption therefore, ranges in its manifestation from bribery and fraud to socio-political transformation of the greatest magnitude. Acts of corruption include:

- Bribery in the public and private sectors
- Embezzlement in the public and private sectors
- Abuse of functions
- Illicit enrichment
- Money laundering
- Concealment and obstruction of justice, among others

The foregoing manifestations of corruption are elegantly evidential in public institutions across third world countries. Ikwen (2014) asserts that corruption and work ethics in the public service are two sides of a coin. She defined work ethics as a group of moral principles, standards of behaviour, or a set of values regarding proper conduct in the workplace. These are usually communicated through organisational values and codes of conduct. She also referred to the public service code of conduct minimum principles to include transparency, integrity, legitimacy, fairness, responsiveness, efficiency and effectiveness (Ikwen, 2014).

Jegede (2017) cites the Indian philosopher and “father of the Indian nation” (1869–1948), Mahatma Gandhi, who traced the roots of corruption to what he described as the seven deadly sins i.e., vices that endanger human virtue. These include wealth without work, pleasure without conscience, knowledge without character, business without ethics, science without humanity, religion without sacrifice, and politics without principle.

Reinforcing the view of corruption as wealth acquired without honest labor, Thomas Jefferson, the third President of the United States (1801–1809), once observed: “I have the consolation of having added nothing to my private fortune during my public service, and retiring with hands as clean as they are empty.”

Again, according to the 8th United States President (1837 – 1841), “to avoid the necessity of a permanent debt and its inevitable consequences, I have advocated and endeavoured to carry into effect the policy of confining the appropriations for public service to such objects only as are clearly within the constitutional authority of the Federal Government”.

Even in third world countries, most of the finances are spent on sophistication and weapons of mass destruction while a greater percentage of the citizens wallow in excruciating poverty, hunger and misery. This amounts to science without humanity and constitutes a national shame to third world countries. Whereas the principle of morality promotes goodness which consist of maintaining, assisting and enhancing life, that of evil destroys, harms or hinders life (Ekang, 2014).

It is observed that in spite of the numerous churches and religious worship places in Nigeria, the country could still be ranked high among the most corrupt countries of the world. According to Jimmy Carter, the 39th United States President (1977 – 1981), “You cannot divorce religious belief and public service. I've never detected any conflict between God's will and my political duty. If you violate one you violate the other”.

Therefore, a public service without moral principles is vulnerable to abuse by the operators of such system. Corruption in the public service borders on stealing of public property or assets or money through bribes, embezzlement, misappropriations and granting illegal discounts or waivers to undeserved people.

The impacts of corruption in the public service include increase in the cost of governance, social and economic inequalities as well as a poor and negative national and international image. Furthermore, corruption perpetuates and exacerbates poverty and distorts the pattern of public expenditure (Ikwen, 2014).

In most third world countries today, corruption is no longer a thing of shame but widely celebrated and applauded by some society members as oiling the wheel of society's progress. It is the system of governance that influences individuals to be corrupt as no one was born corrupt. It is the society that makes man corrupt. Efforts to fight corruption in third world countries have remained largely unsuccessful.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework used in this work is the institutional theory. Institutional theory was introduced in the late 1979 by John Meyer and Brian Rowan as a means to explain how organisations fit with, are related to, and were shaped by their societal, state, national, and global environments. Institutional theory defines the guidelines for social behaviours in the form of accepted structures, schemas, rules, norms, and routines influenced by other members of the collective network of actors. According to this theory, different institutions exist with different structures and mechanisms of social order and cooperation governing the behaviour of societal members.

The basic assumptions of institutional theory are that institutions are governance structures with rules for social conduct; that groups and organisations that conform to these rules are seen as legitimate groups and this enhances their survival and these institutions are characterised by inertia, that is, indisposition to societal change.

In the case of political institutions, apostles of this theory connect corruption to principles of democratic theory. They believe that while developed democracies may have reduced the incidence of conventional corruption, they are also inclined to their own kind of corruption which may even be more dangerous.

Ferretti in Levi and Lord (2011) believe that institutional corruption can always be traced back to the culpable corrupt behaviour of individual agents and that only individuals can be held accountable for corruption.

The relevance of this theory to this work is that different government institutions and structures perform functions that are essential to the survival of the system. The belief is that if all institutions dutifully performed their respective functions properly as are constitutionally assigned to them, then the society would have been better for it. But the tendency is that different institutions fail in performing their constitutionally assigned functions, hence the prevalence of corruption in the society. For example, in Nigeria, anti-corruption institutions established by the government include the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) and Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB). Other agencies and institutions that are empowered to fight corruption directly or indirectly include the Nigeria Police Force (NPF), the Nigeria Custom Service (NCOS), the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corp (NSCDC), etc. It is believed that if all these agencies and institutions performed their duties/functions as are constitutionally provided, then the incidence of corruption would have been reduced to the barest minimum. But whether or not these institutions perform their functions as are assigned by the constitution or the Act of the National Assembly that gives life to them is a matter for further investigation.

However, it is believed that strict adherence to the laws in implementing public policies is the reason developed countries are less prone to corruption than developing or third world countries.

Institutions in third-world countries appear weak in implementing government policies; that is why corruption is rampant. We thus need strong institutions that can successfully implement government policies and not strong individuals because strong individuals cannot implement policies in a weak institution.

Corruption and Human Trafficking in Contemporary International System

Scholars such as Kenb, Ijeoma, Nwamuo, and Anyaoha (2016) strongly contend that corruption constitutes the principal cause of human trafficking within both national and international systems. Corruption represents a breakdown of social values and moral norms, whereby wrong actions are consciously substituted for right ones in pursuit of personal interest or material gain. In a society where corruption permeates the entire system, it is inevitable that many citizens will be drawn into human trafficking, which is often perceived as a lucrative, though an illegal.

The assertion that corruption is one of the major drivers of human trafficking cannot be overstated, as virtually all the channels through which this despicable trade operates are tainted by corruption. Corruption fuels the embers of human trafficking and, in doing so, gives rise to a wide range of associated criminal activities. Human trafficking thrives only among the corrupt and morally depraved; individuals who are disciplined, principled, and ethically grounded cannot partake in such a reprehensible and degrading business.

According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) Report (2006), available data and evidence indicate that the corrupt practices of law enforcement agencies significantly assist traffickers in the recruitment, transportation, and exploitation of victims. Corruption within criminal justice institutions may also obstruct investigations and prosecutions and undermine the effective protection of victims. Moreover, corruption within the private sector that encompasses travel agencies, modelling agencies, marriage bureaus, hotels, construction companies, and similar entities can further facilitate human trafficking. The UNODC Report (2006) further notes that victims of trafficking frequently report the complicity of public officials at every stage of the trafficking process, suggesting that bribery, abuse of office, and the misuse of power by public officials or influential individuals are often integral to the crime.

The recruitment of victims typically involves processes like transfer and transportation. At these early stages of the trafficking chain, bribery and abuse of power emerge as the most commonly reported forms of corruption. These include the facilitation of border crossings without proper scrutiny or with the active cooperation of airline personnel, immigration officers, and visa officials. Victims often recount passing through immigration checkpoints where officials appeared to be complicit in the process. The UNODC Report (2006) illustrates this reality with the following example:

A woman trafficked from South East Asia to Western Europe mentioned that she was instructed by the trafficker to stand in a particular queue at home country's main airport. When she moved to a shorter one, she was moved back to the original queue and it was pointed out to her that the particular immigration official serving this queue was “one of them” and he will not ask any question about her documents.

This is a typical example of how human trafficking operates with the active connivance of corrupt government and security officials who have been bribed or “settled”. Also, some victims claim to have been trafficked using illegally obtained passports, which would be either previously issued documents belonging to others (bought, borrowed or stolen) or “black and white”, or fake passports. The latter are allegedly often acquired through the involvement of corrupt officials in the issuing country (Zhang and Pineda, 2008).

Victims have also reported that often traffickers would mention they had to bribe officials to obtain visas and that the cost of the bribe had been added to the victims' debt toward the trafficker. Victims trafficked into exploitation have repeatedly reported that police and other security operatives would visit their “camp” on a regular basis but would not talk to the women and inspect their situation but would have a coffee with the owner of such “camps”.

Similar cases were reported across Europe. In a few cases in Central and South-Eastern Europe, victims have identified security operatives as their “customers” (Zhang and Pineda, 2008). This speaks volumes about the incident of corruption in the human trafficking ring.

Also, some victims reported that after having escaped or being rescued from a situation of exploitation and having returned home, they were faced with threats from corrupt officials in their own countries. In a number of cases, for instance, victims reported that being apprehended by officials at the airport and held until they or their families paid a bribe.

Sometimes, they were threatened that they would be publicly exposed as prostitutes unless they (the victims) complied by giving them bribes (UNODC, 2006). The most common among the corrupt practices used in trafficking persons are bribery and the abuse of power by border and visa officials. This claim extends further, in some cases, to include actors such as law enforcement and embassy staff. Third world countries are predominantly an origin region for victims of trafficking (Kenb et al., 2016).

Western Europe and Western Africa are reported to be the main destination (sub)regions for African victims. West Africa is also reported to be the main sub-region for victims trafficked from Africa (US State Department, 2011). This points to intra-regional human trafficking in Africa in general and Western Africa in particular.

At a country level, Nigeria ranks very high as an origin country, while Benin Republic, Ghana and Morocco rank high as origin countries (Shelley, 2010). Human trafficking in West Africa usually takes the form of child trafficking within national borders and across the region for labour and sexual exploitation; recruitment of children by force into armed conflicts; and women and girls being trafficked within and out of the region for sexual exploitation, while young men trafficked out are subjected to forced labour, slavery, and organ harvesting for sales and for ritual purposes.

Some of them are subjected to inhuman treatment by the authorities and security operatives of the countries they are trafficked to; most die of psychological trauma, while those who survive suffer mental retardation, as most of them are forced to traffic drugs for their masters/mistresses with the attendant risks of long-term incarceration and possibly a death sentence. All in all, third-world countries are mostly the victims of human trafficking as a result of failure by their respective countries to effectively carry out the functions of government, prompting their citizens to seek greener pastures outside their home countries, where they usually fall prey to human traffickers. The developed countries (first world countries) are usually the destination for these trafficked victims, which makes them the beneficiaries of these illegal trades or dealings in human beings.

Corruption has long been recognised as a significant predictor of human trafficking in countries with a high incidence of trafficking. Bales (2007) identified the importance of governmental corruption in the country or origin as a predictor of trafficking from that country as well as the role of corruption in the country of destination in relation to the permeability of borders, since corruption and particularly bribery of border officials have been found to facilitate border crossing in many countries (Transparency International, 2011).

It has been suggested that trafficking would not be possible without collusion between organised crime groups and corrupt officials (OECD, 2016). Several studies have established a relationship between corruption and organised crime, such as human trafficking in the third world countries (Levi and Lord, 2011; Holmes, 2009; Richard, 2004; PACO, 2002; Plembach, 2016).

Research by Spencer, Broad, Aroma, Junninen, Markina, Saar and Viljanen (2010) focused on the role of corruption in the illegal movement of people across borders, which, although problematic in combining trafficking and smuggling, identified no systematic corruption in the United Kingdom but rather isolated instances of corruption with some key agencies. According to the research, organised immigration offences, cases of individual corruption and bribery were identified, particularly in relation to border crossing and the provision of false documentation. The role of corruption in the processes of human trafficking is widely acknowledged.

Moving victims into some of the developed countries can be achieved in three distinct ways with varying impact on the potential for corruption in the process.

According to the UNODC Report (2016), these include:

- i. Where a victim has legitimate travel documents. In this instance, the vulnerability to corruption is low because there are fewer edges where actors may interact;
- ii. Where the victims travel with forged travel documents, which present vulnerability to bribery and corruption at either the site issuing the forged documents (for example, through officials involved in the provision of passports or work visas) or through interactions at the border and
- iii. Where the victims travel with no documents, which presents vulnerability to bribery at the border crossing by creating the necessity for traffickers to secure the cooperation of a corrupt official in order to facilitate movement.

The opportunity for corruption during the transportation phase will be greater where international borders are crossed, facilitating greater interaction between public officials and traffickers. Although human trafficking may not necessarily involve transnational travel, movement within the UK would involve a lesser risk of corruption given the high level of official scrutiny and absence of interaction between traffickers and public officials. Traffickers may be interested in knowing the various transport routes and common stopping points (i.e., less controlled regulated areas or routes) with the intention of knowing how to “settle” or collude with the officials there in order to enhance their smooth movement of the victims.

The exploitation phase can involve a wide spectrum of legitimate or illegitimate ways of exploiting the victims in such areas as construction, catering, agriculture and food production, in the sex industry, through domestic slavery and through a wide range of criminal markets, including begging, drug cultivation and selling, and shoplifting (UNODC, 2016). These markets provide a common platform in which public and private officials interact with traffickers and thus provide opportunity for corruption to facilitate traffickers' activities.

Beyond the regulation of the labour market, evidence also points to the potential for corruption during the criminal justice process. These officials can perform various corrupt activities to facilitate exploitation or protection of businesses using trafficked victims in exchange for money or sexual services (PACO, 2002) or by providing advance notice of raids or receiving bribes to neglect to conduct raids (Transparency International, 2011).

Corruption of criminal justice officials has also been found to facilitate ineffective and weak investigations and prosecutions in exchange for bribes (UNODC, 2011). Given the low number of reports, investigations and convictions relating to trafficking-related corruption, the risks associated with involvement by potentially corrupt officials are minimal, making the process of engagement by traffickers easier. Apart from the above, there is also the possibility for the manipulation of victims who have had contact with non-governmental organisations (NGOs) / law enforcement and who are re-trafficked. It should also be noted that not only human trafficking but also the deportation and rescue of trafficked victims present business opportunities (Pelmbach, 2016). Programmes aimed at improving the situation in countries of origin are also open to corruption, for example, where the corrupt diversion of resources through anti-trafficking NGOs benefits the elite in the context of development and inequality (Smith, 2010; PACO, 2002).

Public officials charged with overseeing the distribution of funds meant for rehabilitating human trafficking victims are vulnerable to being approached by corrupt officials for diversion of such funds in return for personal financial gain. Furthermore, evidence suggests that the impact of corruption is compounded for women, particularly those facing additional barriers to empowerment in most third-world countries.

Data remain scarce on the role of corruption in human trafficking (UNODC, 2011). Barriers to the collection of reliable data in this area include the reluctance of corrupt officials to talk about their activities; undercover operations are ethically problematic due to the exploitative nature of the activity, and victims are often unable or unwilling to discuss the role of corrupt officials in their victimisation (Smith, 2016; Holmes, 2009).

In all, human trafficking has a serious impact and implications on the rule of law in third-world countries. As an organised crime, trafficking violates the rule of law, threatening national jurisdiction and international law. In all manifestations, trafficking in persons is a violation of human rights, and it causes deprivation and extreme hardship to the victims.

Conclusion

This paper examined the relationship between corruption and human trafficking in the international system, with its impact, specifically on the third-world countries. Although, there are many causes of this problem globally, its continued existence and the difficulties involved in stemming it as a result of corruption, which serves as the hotbed of human trafficking. This corruption revolves around government officials, agencies and institutions entrusted with the duties of stemming the rising tide of corruption in public life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are advanced to checkmate the influence of corruption on human trafficking:

- i. In order to make corruption sufficiently repugnant and unattractive, governments across the world should criminalize it comprehensively and deliberately stigmatize it, presenting it as a disgraceful and dishonourable act so as to deter public patronage and indulgence.
- ii. Security operatives found guilty of corruption or of colluding with criminals to bend or circumvent the law should be summarily dismissed and/or prosecuted. Such conduct gravely compromises national integrity and poses a serious threat to national security.
- iii. Immigration laws and statutes prohibiting human trafficking should be enforced strictly and impartially, to the letter, regardless of status, influence, or vested interests.
- iv. Governments of Third World countries should strengthen state security institutions and other relevant agencies such as the EFCC, ICPC, CCB, and related bodies. Empowering these institutions will enhance effective policy implementation, particularly in the fight against corruption and its associated crimes.

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